

THE GOLDEN AGE OF LITERATURE CREATED BY ALISHER NAVOI

Hojieva Rukhsatbegim Tuymurod qizi

Student of Uzbekistan State World Languages University

khadjievaruxsatbegim1212@gmail.com

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Abstract: The priceless creative and scientific legacy of the great poet and thinker, famous state and public figure Alisher Navoi (1441-1501) occupies a special place not only in the history of our nation, but also in the history of world literature, the development of our national culture and literature.

His full name is Nizamiddin Mir Alisher. He wrote under the pseudonym Navoi in Chigatay (both in Uzbek) and Persian (his works are in Persian). In the West, Chigatoy literature is considered the largest form of Uzbek literature. In general, there is no great person like him among all Turkic people. This article provides information about the life and work of the great poet, reforms in his life, and his legacy.

Key words: philosopher, poet, award, minister, works, requirements, language, statesman, reforms.

Introduction:

On February 9, 1441, in Herat, the famous Uzbek poet, philosopher, and statesman Nizamiddin Mir Alisher was born. The grandfather of Alisher Navoi, who later worked for Shah Rukh and Umar Sheikh, was a distant relative of Amir Temur's son Umar Sheikh. Giyosiddin Bahodir, who was Abulqasim Babur's relative and took part in nation-building, was his father. Sheikh Abusaid Chang, a Kabul nobleman, is the father of her mother.¹

The formative years of Shah Rukh's reign fell during Alisher Navoi's childhood. He was raised among the Temurians, particularly with the future king Hussein Boykaro. He began attending school at the age of 4 and rapidly picked up the ability to read and memorize Turkish and Persian poetry. He speaks Persian well in addition to Uzbek. A power struggle between the pretenders to the throne started after King Shah Rukh's death on March 12, 1447. The Navoi family relocates to Iraq in order to find tranquility. Alisher will visit poet Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi in Taf, the birthplace of the renowned historical masterpiece "Zafarnoma."

Methods:

Alisher started writing poetry when he was 10-12 years old. Historian Khondamir writes that Mawlana Lutfi, who was pleased with the talent of young Navoi:

The window is closed, tears flow from my eyes every moment,

My neck, the rising star, the rising sun

"If possible," he said after hearing his ghazal, "I would exchange my ten to twelve thousand Persian and Turkish verses for this ghazal." At the age of 15, Alisher Navoi rose to

¹ <https://www.savol-javob.com/en/more-about-alisher-navoi/>

fame as a poet. He authored his poems in both Turkish and Persian under the aliases Foni and Navoi.

When Alisher Navoi was 13 or 14 years old, his father passed away. He received his education from Abulqasim Babur and was revered for his exceptional artistic ability. A sudden death also befell Abul Qasim Babur in the spring of 1457. Sultan Abu Said, the sultan of Mowarounnahr, seized control of Khorasan, and the capital was transferred from Samarkand to Herat. On his route to the throne, Husayn Boygaro faced off against Abu Said initially. The main reason Alisher Navoi's family supported Hussein was that they were related, something the new monarch was well aware of. Navoi, who rose to fame as a poet in the nation during this time, was persecuted by Abu Said and banished from Herat. Sultan Abu Said was assassinated in Karabakh in the start of 1469 by his own men. Husayn Boygaro arrived right away and took the throne of Herat after patiently waiting for such an opportunity. Alisher Navoi will visit Herat as well. At the Eid-ul-Fitr reception, Husayn will give Boygaro a copy of his most recent poetry, "Hilaliya".

In capturing Yodgor Muhammad Mirza, Husayn Boygaro's most dangerous political rival, at night, Alisher Navoi exemplifies personal bravery. In appeasing the millions of people who are angry over the new government's high taxes, he acts with fairness and bravery. After these things happened, Alisher Navoi gave his approval for the poet Shaykhim Suhayli Hossein Boygaro, a friend from Samarkand, to be chosen as the government's seal. It was Alisher Navoi's intention to continue serving as a palace advisor and to express his ideas further. But Husayn Boygaro made him a minister in his palace and awarded him the title "Amiri Kabir" in February 1472.

Alisher Navoi concentrated all of his efforts in his new role on bringing about peace and calm in the nation. He started to set up the foundation's business concerns. It places a high value on the growth of trade and crafts in urban areas. Alisher Navoi's efforts have led to a rise in farming culture in the villages. Cities, particularly Herat, are prospering daily.

Like other great characters of the medieval Renaissance, the great humanist Alisher Navoi demonstrated with his entire life what a real person ought to be. He opposed the inequities and injustices of his era, exposed the governmental abuse of power and greed, and shielded the weak and vulnerable. No war of aggression was fought against any nation while Sultan Husayn Boygaro and Alisher Navoi were the prime ministers. Genuine patron of the arts and culture, Prime Minister Alisher Navoi is well renowned for this. He works to effectively resolve social and political issues in his work, treats all social classes and all peoples equally, does not practice any form of discrimination, and pays close attention to the creation of public structures that serve the needs of all.

Results:

In Herat and other cities around the nation in the 1980s, Alisher Navoi allegedly constructed a number of madrasahs, 40 rabats, 17 mosques, 10 residences, 9 baths, 9 bridges, and roughly 20 ponds. Among them are "Ikhlosiya" and "Nizomiya" madrasahs in Herat, "Kholosiya" house, "Shifaiya" tibgahi, "Darul-huffaz" building for Quran reciters, "Khusraviya" madrasa in Marv, "Darul-huffaz" charity center in Mashhad. building and other unique architectural monuments.

Herat saw a golden age of literature during this time. Around Alisher Navoi, a large number of poets—including Shaykhim Suhayli, Khoja Asafi, and Binai—as well as musicians—including Hasan Noi, Khoja Abdulla Marvari, Qulmuhummad Udi, and Shahquli Gijjaki—and

historians—including Mirkhand, Khondamir, Sultanali Mashhadi, and Abdujamil Mashhadi—grew up.

Famous academics like Khoja Hafiz Muhammad, Sultanali Koini, Muhammad Khandan, and Maulana Hijrani were hard at work on their innovative projects, as were artists like Behzad. Harmony was achieved in many areas because to the innovative collaboration of Abdurrahman Jami and Alisher Navoi, two steadfast pillars of the spiritual life of Herat and Khorasan as a whole. The epic "Tuhfat ul-afkor" (1476) dedicated to Jami is Alisher Navoi's first significant work in the Persian language. Alisher Navoi's first significant work in the Uzbek language is the ode "Hiloliya" dedicated to Sultan Husayn Boygaro.

"Badoe ul-bidoya," or "The Beginning of Art," was the first collection of poetry in Uzbek composed by Alisher Navoi in the late 1470s. The 777 ghazals, 85 rubais, 52 masalas, 46 hitsas, 53 fards, 10 tuyuqs, 10 lugzs, 3 mustazads, 5 mukhammas, 3 tarje'bands, and 2 musaddas that make up this divan are listed below. Uzbek poets are not numerous. Navoi. After writing "Badoe' ul-bidoya" in the late 1480s, Alisher Navoi created the divan "Navodir un-nihoya" ("Behad rarities") based on Uzbek poetry. Alisher Navoi wrote "Chikhl Hadis" (also known as "Arbain" or "Forty Hadiths") between 1841 and 1882. This poetically expresses forty hadiths of the Prophet Muhammad (pbuh).

The ghazal, particularly the help for the problem variety, was the most significant poetic form in Alisher Navoi's creative career. The Persian Cabinet received 373 issues from Alisher Navoi. Because of his literary proclivities, he wrote a unique work called "Mufradot" on solving problems in 1485.

Five epics called "Khamsa" were written in the Uzbek language by Alisher Navoi. In 1483–1485 this objective was accomplished. The book became one of Uzbek literature's greatest works and helped Uzbek literature gain a global following.

After "Khamsa," Navoi produced a number of other pieces. He composed the classic poem "Nazm ul-jawahir" in 1485, in which the 4 rhymed verses of rubai tarona (rhyming verses) are used to describe the 266 sage words of Hazrat A, one of the first caliphs.²

The courtiers' resentment of Alisher Navoi's charitable efforts, progressive beliefs, and rise in public renown was brought on by their own selfish objectives. They made an effort to sour relations between the poet and the king. Alisher Navoi was thus removed from his position as prime minister by Husayn Boygaro in 1487, and Muhammad Majdiddin assumed that position. Navoi is chosen to lead Astrobad as governor. The city and region of Astrobad developed, positive connections with surrounding nations were established, and trade relations were established during Navoi's two years as governor. In addition, Alisher Navoi addressed letters to his friends in Herat and composed a number of new poetry in Astrobad. His letter from Astrobad to Badiuzzamont, the eldest son of Husayn Boygaro, can be called a treatise on state administration.

Alisher Navoi always dreamed of seeing Husayn Boykara as a just and enlightened ruler. In his letters to Husayn Boygaro from Astrobad and other officials, he calls on them to be honest and fair, to establish a solid order in the state administration system, and to implement some reforms. But Alisher Navoi's dreams were hard to come true. Shah Alisher allows Navoi to return to Herat after rumors spread in Astrabad that damaged the

²<http://www.elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/referatlar-mustaqil-ish-kurs-ishi/item/14371>

relationship between Navoi and Husayn Boygaro. Hossein Boygaro offers Navoi several high positions. After Alisher Navoi did not agree, he was given the official title of "Muqarrabi Hazrat Sultani" ("The closest person to His Majesty the Sultan"). With this, he was able to meet the king and meddle in all state affairs. As a result, Muhammad Majdiddin and the other palace officials had to concur with him on all significant issues for a very long time. However, a lot of people were aware of the tense bond Alisher Navoi had with Majdiddin. Additionally, it is known that the governor of Balkh, Darveshali Majdiddin, rebelled against the federal administration. Navoi's intervention put an end to this insurrection. Majdiddin left politics in 1490 mostly as a result of this incident.³

Alisher Navoi has always wished to carry out more original research and develop his ideas. And his plans had to be modified by life. Scholar and poet Pahlavon Muhammad passed away in 1493, Sayyid Hasan Ardasher passed away in 1488, and Jami passed away in 1492. Navoi penned the pamphlets "Holoti Sayyid Hasan Ardasher", "Khamsat ul-mutahayirin" ("Five Miracles"), and "Holoti Pahlavon Muhammad" to honor these nobles' memories and show his appreciation for them. He started Tarikhi Muluki Ajam (History of the Kings of Ajam) in Astrobad and concluded it in 1489.

In the manner of Jami's "Bahoristan" and Davlatshah Samarkandi's "Tazkirat ush-shuaro," he started writing the tazkirah "Majolis un-nafois" ("Complex of Studies") about contemporary poets in 1490, and he completed it in 1492. The scientific manual "Mezon ul-avzon" ("Measure of the Scales") on the theory of poetry in the Uzbek language—specifically, the laws of Aruz weight—was written by Alisher Navoi around this time. He assembled his Turkish letters into a complex known as "Munshaot" (literally, "Letters") in 1494. Under the name "Nasayim ul-muhabbat" ("Winds of Love"), he translated Jami's "Nafahot ul-uns" in 1495, edited it, and added fresh details about Turkish heroes. As a result, "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat" can be regarded as Alisher Navoi's own independent work.⁴

Conclusion:

A new comprehensive collection of all of Alisher Navoi's Turkish poems was started in 1491–1422, and it was finished in 1498–1499. The book is known as "Khazayin ul-Maani" (the "Treasure of Meanings") in its overall form, and "The Book of Chor" since it is divided into 4 parts. Devon contains all of Alisher Navoi's poetry, which reflects his feelings, outlook on the world, and aspirations. Around this time, Alisher Navoi produced "Devoni Foniy" and two volumes of odes in Persian, which were poems written in Persian. The fact that Alisher Navoi wrote works in Farsi indicates that he was aware of the spiritual requirements of the majority of Farsi-speaking people in Khurasan.

In his poetic and prose works, the great poet showed the high universal ideas of our native language, incomparable vocabulary and limitless possibilities of expression with all the charm and elegance, and won a worthy and solid place in the hearts of millions of readers on earth.

³ www.savol-javob.com/en/great-thinker-sultan-of-gha...her-navoi-1441-1501/

⁴ <https://arboblar.uz/uz/people/alisher-navoi>

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